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Khasenov Madi

Kazakh-British Technical University

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HYBRID ARIMAX-LSTM MODEL TO PREDICT AIR POLLUTION

Abstract.

Air pollution has a severe impact on public health and the environment. It is crucial to provide people with an air quality prediction tool to minimize health risks in the most affected areas. This study proposes a hybrid model that combines the auto-regressive integrated moving average with exogenous variables (ARIMAX) and long-short-term memory (LSTM) to predict air pollution levels. The ARIMAX model uses historical meteorological and air quality data, while the LSTM model captures complex nonlinear patterns in the residuals of ARIMAX predictions. With this approach, our hybrid model addresses the limitations of traditional and standalone models, achieving significant improvements in predictive accuracy. Experimental results show that our hybrid model outperforms individual ARIMAX and LSTM models, with a 31.9% improvement over ARIMAX and a 16.7% improvement over LSTM. This hybrid model offers a powerful tool for predicting air pollution levels that can be used in various domains, such as smart city applications.

Keywords: Air Pollution Prediction, ARIMAX Model, LSTM Model, Hybrid Model, Time Series Analysis, Deep Learning, Machine Learning.

1. Introduction

Air pollution is a serious problem that affects millions of people around the world every day. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), 99% of the world's population lives in regions where the amount of pollutants exceeds the air quality norms [1]. High concentrations of these harmful particles result in an increased risk of diseases such as stroke, lower respiratory diseases, heart disease, and cancer. In 2019, an estimated 4.2 million people died from premature death due to diseases caused by air pollution. Most of these deaths occurred in low- and middle-income countries with the highest exposure to fine particles [2].

The effects of air pollution can also be indirect. Air pollutants can acidify soils and fresh water and damage crops by weakening photosynthesis, affecting world security. Approximately 4% of annual global crop yield is lost due to air pollution [3]. Large amounts of fine particles also contribute to climate change, thus resulting in probable future droughts, water scarcity, forest fires, and flooding [4], [5].

Multiple causes of air pollution in urban areas exist, including coal-fueled power plants, vehicle emissions, by-products of manufacturing, and garbage waste burning. Many countries have successfully implemented policies that help reduce the impact of these factors; however, the most vulnerable continue to suffer from the consequences of high levels of air pollution.

It is important to urge governments to take action, drawing on the successful experiences of other countries. However, until this happens, it is also crucial to have the tools to know the current level of air pollution and forecast it for the near future. This will help people avoid getting exposed to fine particles or prepare for them accordingly beforehand.

In this study, we propose a hybrid model that integrated autoregressive integrated moving average with exogenous variable (ARIMAX) with long short-term

memory (LSTM) to predict air pollution levels. Our approach combines both traditional statistical models and modern deep learning techniques to achieve improved forecasting results. The proposed hybrid model addresses the limitations of standalone forecasting models by integrating ARIMAX's strength in capturing linear relationships with LSTM's ability to model complex nonlinear dependencies, hence resulting in a better predictive accuracy.

2. Literature Review

In recent years, numerous studies have focused on developing models to predict air quality accurately. The approaches vary from traditional time series analysis to advanced machine learning techniques.

Yuxuan Cao et al. proposed a hybrid model to forecast air pollution levels based on metrics from various monitoring stations. The model integrated the extended Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model with the Empirical Mode Decomposition (EMD) method and truncated Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). The experiment indicated that the proposed model outperformed traditional air quality forecasting models. However, the main limitation of their study was that only the historical data was used to make the predictions, meaning other factors such as weather or traffic were not taken into account [6].

Abdellatif Bekkar et al. in their study compared traditional models, such as Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM), Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (Bi-LSTM), Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU), Bi-GRU (Bidirectional Gated Recurrent Unit), Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) with their hybrid CNN-LSTM model. Experimental results showed that the hybrid CNN-LSTM model provides more accurate air quality predictions than other algorithms. A notable limitation of this study is that the experiment was based only on data collected in Beijing, China [7].

S. John Livingston et al. analyzed multiple state-of-the-art algorithms, such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Support Vector Regression (SVR), Random Forest (RF), Random Forest Regression (RFR), Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Recurrent Neural Network (RNN), and Federated Learning (FL) to determine the best-performing model based on their prediction accuracy. They concluded that models based on SVR and RFR provide the best prediction results. The study's limitation, again, is that it is based solely on data from Beijing [8].

En Xin Neo et al. proposed an air quality predictive model based on machine learning and deep learning techniques, including Ada Boost, SVR, RF, K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN), Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), and LSTM. What makes their study stand out is the use of meteorological data. Researchers aimed to enhance the prediction in existing models by removing irrelevant features. They found that the LSTM model performed the best after being feature-optimized. The enhanced LSTM model also suggested that humidity and wind speed play key roles in air quality prediction [9].

Shorouq Al-Eidi et al. aimed to find the most effective air quality predictive model. Researchers used regression techniques, including Random Forest, Linear, and Decision Tree regression. The study found that the Decision Tree regression model performed better than the other two models in predicting air quality. The

incorporation of Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) and SMOTER techniques had a huge impact on enhancing the model accuracy. However, this study does not investigate the effect of weather data on air quality, which researchers mention [10].

Existing air quality prediction models show significant advancements in providing accurate results. However, several limitations and gaps exist across the studies. Many models only rely on historical data without considering external factors like weather conditions, industrial activities, and traffic. These factors influence the levels of air quality, and it is important to take them into account. Additionally, some studies focused exclusively on data from one city, e.g., Beijing, thus making it hard to adjust the findings to other places.

Further enhancing air quality prediction models requires addressing these limitations by implementing a more efficient and adaptable approach.

3. Materials and Methods

To address the above-mentioned limitations, we use a hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model to forecast the air quality [11]. The detailed workflow of this hybrid model is shown in Figure 1. First, we start with collecting historical Air Quality and Meteorological data. Then we prepare the data, split it, and train both ARIMAX and LSTM models. The next step is to generate predictions for both models and combine them. Finally, we evaluate the performance of our model.

Figure 1. Flow Chart of the Hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM Model for Prediction.

3.1. Data Collection

We start with collecting data for our model, namely historical Air Quality and Meteorological data. Our goal is to find trends and correlations between them, which will help us predict air pollution levels.

For Air Quality data we use records gathered by the U.S. Embassy & Consulate in Kazakhstan [12]. The data collected by the U.S. Embassy consists of the number of $PM_{2.5}$, and PM_{10} particles, NO_2 , SO_2 , and CO levels for the past four years. PM stands for Particulate Matter, it is used to categorize fine particles by their

size: $PM_{2.5}$ is used for particles that are $2.5 \mu\text{m}$ and smaller, while PM_{10} refer to particles that are $10 \mu\text{m}$ and smaller. The values of these categories help us understand the level of air pollution.

The weather data is collected from visualcrossing [13], a service that provides meteorological data and API. The records contain the information about temperature, humidity, precipitation, speed of wind, UV index, and other related data.

3.2. ARIMAX Model

The ARIMAX Model is an extension of ARIMA Model that used exogenous (independent) variables to improve the quality of predictions. It is useful when the target variable is influenced by external factors, which is what happens in our case. ARIMAX consists of the following components: AR (AutoRegressive), I (Integrated), MA (Moving Average), X (Exogenous Variables).

The AR component models the target variable as a function of its own previous values. The AR(p) model of order (p) is given by:

$$y_t = c + \varphi_1 y_{t-1} + \varphi_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + \varphi_p y_{t-p} + \epsilon_t \quad (1)$$

The Integrated component deals with differencing the data to make it stationary. If the data needs to be differenced d times to achieve stationarity, we denote this by $I(d)$. The differenced series is:

$$\Delta^d y_t = y_t - y_{t-d} \quad (2)$$

The MA component models the target variable as a function of past error terms. The MA(q) model of order q is given by:

$$y_t = \mu + \epsilon_t + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} \quad (3)$$

The X component includes external predictors that can influence the target variable. If there are k exogenous variables $x_{i,t}$ the model includes terms for these variables:

$$y_t = \beta_1 x_{1,t} + \beta_2 x_{2,t} + \dots + \beta_k x_{k,t} \quad (4)$$

The full ARIMAX model after combining all components is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta^d y_t = c + \varphi_1 \Delta^d y_{t-1} + \varphi_2 \Delta^d y_{t-2} + \dots + \varphi_p \Delta^d y_{t-p} + \theta_1 \epsilon_{t-1} + \theta_2 \epsilon_{t-2} + \dots + \theta_q \epsilon_{t-q} + \beta_1 x_{1,t} + \beta_2 x_{2,t} + \dots + \beta_k x_{k,t} + \epsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Although ARIMAX is powerful for capturing linear relationships in time series data and accounting for exogenous variables, it has its limitations. The model assumes the data is stationary, meaning it performs best when the statistical properties of the data do not change over time. When air pollution levels vary due to irregular external factors, such as sudden weather changes or unexpected emissions, ARIMAX fails to provide reliable forecasts. It is also not as effective at capturing nonlinear patterns and long-term dependencies.

3.3. LSTM Model

LSTM is a type of a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) model. LSTM is designed to handle long time series data, and it addresses the problem of vanishing and exploding gradients in traditional RNNs. This

makes LSTM more effective for tasks that involve long sequences.

The architecture of LSTMs includes cell states and gates that control the flow of information. The main components of an LSTM include: Cell State, Hidden State, Input Gate, Forget Gate, and Output Gate.

The input gate decides on whether to let the new data in. The equation is given by:

$$i_t = \sigma(W_i \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_i) \quad (6)$$

The forget gate is responsible for deleting data that is no longer needed. The expression is following:

$$f_t = \sigma(W_f \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_f) \quad (7)$$

The output gate determines what information to output. The formula can be written as:

$$o_t = \sigma(W_o \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_o) \quad (8)$$

The candidate cell state contains the potential new information to be added to the cell state. The computation is given by:

$$\tilde{C}_t = \tanh(W_C \cdot [h_{t-1}, x_t] + b_C) \quad (9)$$

The cell states are updated by combining the new candidate cell state with the old cell state. The equation is:

$$C_t = f_t C_{t-1} + i_t \tilde{C}_t \quad (10)$$

The hidden state is updated based on the new cell state and the output gate. The formula is following:

$$h_t = o_t \tanh(C_t) \quad (11)$$

LSTM models excel at recognizing nonlinear dependencies and long-term trends, which makes them optimal for time series forecasting. However, they require large datasets for effective training and can be computationally expensive.

3.4. Hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM Model

The hybrid model proposed in this research combines the strengths of ARIMAX and LSTM models to improve the accuracy of air pollution predictions. While ARIMAX excels at capturing linear relationships in time series data, LSTM is adept at modeling complex, non-linear dependencies. However, instead of merely combining predictions from these models directly, we introduce a meta-model to intelligently integrate their outputs, leveraging a data-driven approach to determine the optimal contribution of each base model.

The Workflow of the Hybrid Model is as follows:

1. ARIMAX Component: The ARIMAX model is trained on the input time series data to predict the target variable (e.g., $PM_{2.5}$ levels).

2. Residual Modeling with LSTM: The residuals from the ARIMAX predictions, calculated as the difference between the actual values and ARIMAX predictions, are modeled using the LSTM network. This ensures that the hybrid model captures the non-linear patterns left unaddressed by the ARIMAX component.

3. Meta-Model Integration: The final step involves integrating predictions from both ARIMAX and LSTM using a meta-model. The meta-model combines these outputs in a weighted fashion, where the weights are learned from the data itself, optimizing the contribution of each base model to minimize overall prediction error.

Let y_t represent the actual value of the target variable at time t . The predictions from the ARIMAX and

LSTM models are denoted as $\hat{y}_{ARIMAX,t}$ and $\hat{y}_{LSTM,t}$, respectively. The residuals modeled by LSTM are given by:

$$r_t = y_t - \hat{y}_{ARIMAX,t} \quad (12)$$

The LSTM is trained to predict these residuals, producing \hat{r}_t , which represents the model's estimate of the non-linear components.

The combined prediction from the ARIMAX-LSTM hybrid model is:

$$\hat{y}_{Hybrid,t} = \hat{y}_{ARIMAX,t} + \hat{r}_t \quad (13)$$

Incorporating the meta-model, the final hybrid prediction is expressed as a weighted combination of the base models' predictions:

$$\hat{y}_t = \alpha \cdot \hat{y}_{ARIMAX,t} + \beta \cdot \hat{y}_{LSTM,t} + \gamma \quad (14)$$

where α , β , and γ are parameters learned by the meta-model. These parameters are optimized on a validation set to minimize the prediction error, such as Mean Absolute Error (MAE) or Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). For a detailed look at the model architecture and code, refer to our GitHub repository [14].

4. Results and Application

In this section we evaluate our proposed model on the datasets mentioned before, and compare it with the traditional standalone models. We also explore possible applications of our findings.

4.1. Experimental Setup

A personal computer is used to run all the experiments. The specifications are Apple M1 CPU and 8GB RAM. The computer is ran on MacOS Sonoma 14.2 with Python 3.11.5. Numerous extension packages were used in the experiments, including sklearn, tensorflow, statsmodels, matplotlib, pmdarima, pandas, numpy, and glob.

4.2. Data Preprocessing

Our data needs to be prepared to successfully train the models. First, we clean our data, i.e. handle all the missing or unnecessary values we have. In our case, we used mean imputation for $PM_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , NO_2 , SO_2 , and CO columns. We then dropped the columns from the meteorological data that does not affect the air pollution levels, such as time of sunrise and sunset, type of precipitation, textual weather description and others.

After that, we create lag features for one and seven days to the data. This helps the models capture seasonal patterns in the data. Then, we normalize the data ensuring that our records are consistent in type. Finally, we split our records into training, validation, and testing datasets, performing a 60-20-20 split.

4.3. Model Training and Evaluation

4.3.1. Training the ARIMAX Model

To train the model, we first need to determine the appropriate values of parameters (p, d, q). The differencing parameter (d) was estimated using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test. This test checks if the unit root is present in the series, which helps us to determine whether differencing is needed.

Next, we evaluate different combinations of (p, d, q) parameters by performing a grid search over possible

values. For each combination, an ARIMAX model is trained using exogenous variables, and its performance is measured using the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC). The model with the lowest AIC is selected as the optimal configuration. In our experiment, we determined the optimal parameters of (p, d, q) to be (1, 1, 2).

The next thing we do is fitting the ARIMAX model using the estimated parameters.

4.3.2. Training the LSTM Model

LSTM networks expect the data to be in a [samples, timesteps, features] format, so we reshape it accordingly. Then, we define the model architecture by specifying the layers of the model. The following step is to compile the model using the mean squared error loss and Adam optimizer.

We now train the LSTM model on the residuals from the ARIMAX model.

4.3.3. Hybrid Model Prediction

After training ARIMAX on the testing set and LSTM on the residuals from the ARIMAX model, we combine both predictions to get the merged prediction.

$$MP = AP + LP \quad (15)$$

where MP stands for Merged Predictions, AP for ARIMAX Predictions, and LP for LSTM Predictions.

Then we prepare the meta data to train the meta model. It is formed by combining the base model predictions:

$$\text{meta_data} = [\hat{y}_{ARIMAX} \cdot \hat{y}_{LSTM}] \quad (16)$$

The meta model is used to learn how to best combine the predictions from both models, thus providing a more efficient result. It can be represented as:

$$\hat{y}_{final} = \alpha \cdot \hat{y}_{ARIMAX} + \beta \cdot \hat{y}_{LSTM} + \gamma \quad (17)$$

4.3.4. Evaluation Metrics

We use Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) and Mean Absolute Error for evaluating the performance of our proposed model. RMSE can be expressed as:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \quad (18)$$

And the formula for MAE is given by:

$$MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \quad (19)$$

where y_i represents the actual value, and \hat{y}_i represents the predicted value.

4.4. Results and Analysis

We compare our Hybrid model with standalone ARIMAX and LSTM models to evaluate its performance. As shown in the Table 1, we can see that our proposed ARIMAX-LSTM model excels significantly compared to the LSTM model, and gives us a slightly better result when comparing to the ARIMAX model. Specifically, our hybrid model shows 31.9% improvement in RMSE over the standalone ARIMAX model, and 16.7% improvement over the LSTM model for RMSE. This reduction in error metrics suggests that the hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model effectively captures both linear and nonlinear patterns in the data.

Table 1.

Evaluation metrics of different methods.

Method	RMSE	MAE
ARIMAX	32.90	29.41
LSTM	26.89	20.75
Hybrid	22.40	17.39

4.5. Model Testing on Santiago, Chile

To evaluate the generalizability of the hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model, we tested it on data from Santiago, Chile. Santiago was chosen for two primary reasons. First, it provides an opportunity to assess how well the model performs in a different geographical and climatic context. Second, Santiago shares similar geographical conditions with Almaty, Kazakhstan, such as being surrounded by mountains, which can exacerbate

air pollution by trapping pollutants. However, the air quality in Santiago is significantly better compared to Almaty.

The model's performance in Santiago is summarized in Table 2. These results indicate that the hybrid model slightly outperformed ARIMAX and LSTM in terms of accuracy in Santiago as well. This suggests that the proposed hybrid model is robustness.

Table 2.

Evaluation metrics of different methods tested on Santiago, Chile.

Method	RMSE	MAE
ARIMAX	37.37	33.30
LSTM	23.95	18.60
Hybrid	21.93	18.13

4.5.1. Comparison of Air Quality in Santiago and Almaty

Although Santiago and Almaty share geographical similarities, the air quality in Santiago is notably better. Research indicates several reasons for this difference:

1. Regulation of Vehicle Emissions: Santiago has implemented stringent vehicle emissions standards, including the restriction of older, high-polluting vehicles and the promotion of low-emission public transport.
2. Cleaner Energy Policies: Chile has heavily invested in renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind power, reducing reliance on fossil fuels.
3. Industrial Emission Controls: Industries in Santiago are subject to stricter environmental regulations, limiting the amount of pollutants they can release into the atmosphere.
4. Public Awareness Campaigns: Santiago has conducted extensive public awareness campaigns encouraging citizens to adopt environmentally friendly practices.

4.5.2. Recommendations for Almaty, Kazakhstan

To improve air quality in Almaty, similar measures could be considered:

1. Upgrade Vehicle Standards: Introduce stricter emissions standards for vehicles and phase out older, high-emission cars.
2. Promote Clean Energy: Expand the use of renewable energy sources to reduce dependence on coal and other fossil fuels.
3. Enforce Industrial Regulations: Implement stricter industrial emission controls to reduce pollutants released by factories.
4. Improve Public Transport: Invest in low-emission public transport systems to reduce the number of private vehicles on the roads.

5. Increase Public Awareness: Launch campaigns to educate the public on the effects of air pollution and promote environmentally friendly habits.

By adopting these measures, Almaty could potentially replicate Santiago's success in mitigating air pollution and improving overall air quality.

4.6. Application

Our proposed hybrid model overcomes the limitations of standalone forecasting models by combining the strengths of ARIMAX and LSTM. While ARIMAX effectively captures linear patterns, LSTM excels at modeling complex nonlinear relationships. This approach enhances the model's reliability, making it more accurate in forecasting.

The hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model provides a powerful tool for predicting air pollution levels. It can be applied in multiple domains, including real-time air quality monitoring, agricultural planning, emission forecasting, infrastructure development, smart city applications, and citizen engagement. In each of these domains, our model could be used to mitigate the effects of bad air quality by preventive warning.

We offer a prototype of a mobile smart city application that could be used as an early-warning tool for citizens (see Fig. 2). The application will be using real-time data from multiple stations across the city to show current air pollution levels, and by using historical meteorological and air quality data it will show the accurate air quality forecast. This application will be a powerful tool that helps people protect themselves from unnecessary exposure to fine particles, and minimize the future contact with them too.

Figure 2. Prototype of an Air Quality Prediction Application.

5. Discussion

5.1. Implications

Our hybrid model offers a robust tool for predicting air pollution levels, which potentially can be used in various domains. Some of them include agricultural planning, emission forecasting, smart city applications and so on. The model can help policymakers and urban planners make appropriate decisions to fight impacts of air pollution on public health and the environment. We offer a prototype of a smart city application that could be used as an early-warning tool for the citizens, allowing them to minimize the exposure to harmful pollutants.

5.2. Limitations and Future Work

Despite the promising results, our study has some limitations. The model's performance greatly depends on the availability of historical air quality and meteorological data. In regions with limited data, the model's accuracy might be low.

Future research will focus on expanding the model to include other important factors such as traffic data, industrial activities, and natural disasters. These factors could significantly improve the accuracy of our model.

By addressing these limitations, future iterations of the hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model can provide even more accurate results in forecasting air pollution levels,

which would contribute more to the protection of public health.

6. Conclusions

This study proposes a hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model for predicting air pollution levels. Our model combines the advantages of traditional statistical methods and advanced deep learning techniques. The results of our experiments show that the hybrid model outperforms individual ARIMAX and LSTM models, achieving significant improvements in predictive accuracy. Specifically, our proposed hybrid model demonstrated a 31.9% improvement over the standalone ARIMAX model, and a 16.7% improvement over the LSTM model. These findings suggest that the hybrid ARIMAX-LSTM model successfully captured both linear and nonlinear patterns in the data, which led to more accurate air quality forecasting.

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